

THE IMPACT OF MULTIMEDIA IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROBLEM SOLVING SKILLS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL

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Abstract

This paper discusses the potential benefits of an interactive Multimedia information representation in enhancing students' problem solving aligned with in learning amongst Secondary School students. Multimedia intends to bring the fundamental changes in problem solving capacity of the students by bridging the gap between theory and practice. The use of multimedia creates a powerful and flexible learning environment with problem solving vision of teaching and learning. The key elements of the interactive Multimedia (e.g. multiple media, user control, interactivity and use of timelines and concept maps) were then considered to improve the learning process. The conclusion of this study is supportive of the positive value of the use Multimedia to enhance the problem solving of the secondary school students.

Keywords: multimedia-based learning and critical thinking skills.

Introduction

The infusion of multimedia technology into education has created a significant impact on the instructional content development and the methods of communicating information to learners. This leads to the evolution of new concepts and innovative teaching techniques in the instruction-learning process, changing the way teachers teach and students learn. This changing landscape of education focuses on learning, rather than on teaching and pedagogy, curriculum instruction and the development of critical thinking.

It seeks to create a generation of learners whose learning is defined as "the ability to retain, synthesize, and apply conceptually complex information in meaningful ways" (Lambert & McCombs, 1998). It also encourages better student learning through the learning objectives of project-based learning, or learning by doing (Schank, Berman and Macpherson, 1999), and to

enable problem solving , creativity and communication to take place in the classroom (Bates, 2000). In addition to these, multimedia technology has been shown to affect students' critical thinking and motivate their self-esteem levels, as well as allow them to become creative and self-directed thinkers (Agnew, Kellerman & Meyer, 1996)

The present paper discusses the use of Multimedia in the classroom teaching which helps in the development of student ability in acquiring problem-solving skills. It also highlights the benefit and challenges of multimedia in the classroom teaching.

Problem Solving

Problem based learning is generally considered to be a student-centred, inquiry and/or discovery based strategy which challenges students to become active participants in the learning process. This process is usually encouraged through group work with the teacher acting as a facilitator or mentor in the learning process. However, the extent to which this challenge is being taken up by students in the conventional classroom setting is very much dependent upon the enthusiasm and knowledge of the instructor. Historically, for effective learning to take place.

If teachers are to assist students in the acquisition of process skills through problem based learning then they need to provide students with the opportunities to experience 'real world' scenarios that challenge and extend their thinking ability. Teachers need to provide a framework to encourage initiative and refine strategies and skills, together with a development of adequate background knowledge, in guiding students towards constructing a solution(s) to the assigned task.

Problem based learning in involves the development of skills which enable the student to identify problems, form hypotheses, search for and collate information through observation and measurement, interpret and analyse data, and propose a solution. In a sense, the concept of problem solving through a student inquiry approach has strong association with the related developments in the ideas of 'constructivism'. According to this emerging theory, students need to construct their own understanding of each scientific concept presented to them. The

understanding that the student develops in any learning situation is influenced by his or her own prior knowledge and experience or belief structure. The student has the responsibility for her/his own learning and the acquisition of knowledge involves construction of meaning from the stimulus material presented and is part of a continuous active process. Once constructed the knowledge is evaluated and either accepted or rejected by the learner thus becoming part of their belief structure.

Within this framework, the primary role of teaching is not in the transfer of knowledge through lecture or explanation, but in the creation of a series of situations that will enable students to cultivate understanding. This understanding will occur through developing the necessary mental constructions in a meta-cognitive approach to the learning process.

In promoting the development of students, strategies which focus on a problem solving approach, include:

- developing student self-esteem and confidence through greater involvement in the learning process;
- encouraging student centred lessons involving cooperation and communication between group members;
- providing opportunities for student creativity, initiative and persistence; and
- presenting students with challenges that develop new skills.

As discussed earlier, the steps in the problem solving process involve skills that can be identified and developed in all students. Some of these are quite simple manipulative skills but others involve complex thinking abilities. Teaching the problem solving process requires that the instructor has knowledge of the problem solving abilities that students bring to the classroom and further can develop these skills to the benefit of the student.

Multimedia in Education

The use of multimedia in industries has been extensive, as it has been effective in increasing productivity and retention rates, where research has shown that people remember 20% of what they see, 40% of what they see and hear, but about 75% of what they see and hear and do simultaneously (Lindstrom, 1994). This is especially significant in the CBT (Computer-Based Training) modules in corporations like Ernst & Young, and Union Pacific, where employees

are trained in organisational procedure, and in flight simulations in the aviation industry to train pilots. It is now permeating the educational system as a tool for effective teaching and learning. With multimedia, the communication of the information can be done in a more effective manner and it can be an effective instructional medium for delivering information. A multi-sensory experience can be created for the audience, which, in turn, elicits positive attitudes toward the application.

Definitions

Multimedia source(s):

Any single item or set of items combining text with audio, video, or images for the purpose of conveying information leading to meaning in the mind of a learner.

Multimedia, defined, is the combination of various digital media types such as text, images, sound and video, into an integrated multi-sensory interactive application or presentation to convey a message or information to an audience. In other words, multimedia means “an individual or a small group using a computer to interact with information that is represented in several media, by repeatedly selecting what to see and hear next” (Agnew et. al, 1996).

Multimedia has also been shown to elicit the highest rate of information retention and result in shorter learning time (Ng and Komiya, 2000; Hofstetter, 1995). On the part of the creator, designing a multimedia application that is interactive and multi-sensory can be both a challenge and a thrill. Multimedia application design offers new insights into the learning process of the designer and forces him or her to represent information and knowledge in a new and innovative way (Agnew, Kellerman & Meyer, 1996).

Multimedia information is a combination of images, picture and sound which can be represented, disseminated and conveyed through diverse means and strategies. Previous researches on collaborative construction of information representations have shown positive results for both the learning processes and learning outcomes. Different field of study have different possibility of the use of multimodal representation. Different information representation and organization influence on the human cognitive process. The effect of a

multimodal information representation in the learning material has shown positive results in the domain of science and technology as well as the individual use of these multiple presentation.

Multimedia Classroom

The time it takes to earn the degree in education today is based on an increasingly outdated model: so many hours in a classroom entitle a student to a receipt in the form of a grade, and so many receipts can be redeemed for a credential in the form of a degree... Education today is just beginning to think of shifting the basis of certification from time served to skills and knowledge obtained.

Traditionally classroom situation is teachers stand in front of the students, giving explanations, informing, and instructing. They usually use chalk to write something on the blackboard. These technique needs slightly to be modified regarding with the development of the technology. The using of multimedia in classroom cannot be denied anymore. That will make possible for teachers giving more opportunity to students being happier and more enjoy during the course which enhances the critical thinking among secondary school students. Traditional classrooms have different settings from the multimedia classrooms. Students seat in rows and a chalkboard in the front. The teacher is standing in front of the class giving a lecture. Compared with traditional classrooms, multimedia classrooms setting differ greatly from traditional classrooms. Traditional classrooms have the seats in rows and a chalkboard in the front. In the multimedia classrooms, students' seat can be modified according to the situation needed. Inside the classrooms, all the equipment is available and makes the students feel comfortable to study. The use of multimedia described here makes use of print texts, film and Internet to develop and enhance linguistics and critical thinking within the students. Through their interactions with multimedia texts on topic of interest, students become increasingly familiar with academic vocabulary and language structures.

As they pursue sustained study of one content area through focus discipline research, the students become actively engaged in the process of meaning construction within and across different media. Working though the complex intermingling of meanings, embedded within different texts encourages students to make connections as they build a wider range of schemata, which are then available to help them grasp future texts. Using print, film and

Internet as resources for studying provides students with opportunities to gather information through stimuli that will stimulate their imaginations, engage their interest and introduce them to the raw materials for analysis and interpretation of both language and context. Students develop solid foundation in several subject areas and their overall knowledge base, as well as their English language and critical literacy skills, facilitating their performance in future college courses.

The use of multimedia program is presented as a simulation game to interest and motivation. Students using the program found themselves in the virtual world of education.

Benefits

Personalized education: Learning and teaching with the assistance of technologies benefit both students who are able to process information easily and students who need more time to learn and digest study content. In addition, students can complete the instructional goal through self-learning in instances where teachers are not able to provide individual consultation.

Flexibility of time and space: The multimedia learning platform allows students to suspend and revisit study material at their convenience and within a flexible time frame.

Comfortable for a variety of personality types: A multimedia learning platform environment is impartial. The introverted student, for example, has the opportunity to function in a comfortable learning environment that provides privacy and independent operation, without pressure from classmates or a professor.

Diversified teaching materials: The multimedia platform provides diversified teaching materials through text, music, pictures and animation which can provide assistance to students' cognitive development.

Effective teaching materials: Presentations using multimedia applications can encourage student learning and effectively integrate a variety of media elements. The multimedia learning platform can also stimulate situational applications, allowing students to understand the subject more easily and observe its relevance.

Effective motivation: The attractive live designs and audio and flash effects included in a multimedia platform can attract interest and encourage student edification.

Challenges

Teaching process quickened by multimedia equipments: Teachers don't have to write on blackboard when using multimedia equipments, which on the one hand, saves much time. On the other hand, it causes disadvantages. Most teachers cannot control rhythm of class, quickening teaching process. Thus students are passively led by PPT and cannot think actively in class.

Foster laziness among teachers: Many teachers use the same PPT when teaching the same lesson. They don't change contents on PPT according to students' reaction and pay no attention to explore teaching patterns. In the long run teachers become lazy and don't fully prepare for every class.

Lack of communications and interactions between students and teachers: After introducing multimedia equipments into class, some teachers just sit behind the computers and play the PPT. Students can only hear teacher's voice but cannot see the person. Therefore, students cannot communicate with teachers. Because of lack of interaction, teachers don't know students' reaction and cannot control teaching procedure. Thus, throughout the whole class, teachers talk with no enthusiasm, and students listen without passion, compromising teaching quality.

Harm students' creativity: If teachers just sit behind computers and don't communicate with students to lead them to think and evoke their thoughts, it will harm students' creative thinking ability.

Recommendations for applications of Multimedia

Multimedia technology offers an easier and even faster environment to access and retrieve information. Children can retrieve information much more rapidly using Internet service, but it doesn't necessarily mean that children have the ability to evaluate the validity of information, nor does it mean that the information they acquire from the Internet will trigger them to think deeply. Nelson states that, "true learning is not so much about the gathering of information as it is about using and analyzing information. The Internet does not promote this level of thinking" (2000, p. 47). Essentially, education should prepare students to be creative thinkers and develop the needed models and purpose for learning. Therefore, the goal of teaching and learning should be focused on training students to think critically and giving them opportunities to build

up their own thinking experiences they implement the future teaching model. The educators should pay more attention to how instructions are delivered to students and how the learning objectives should be achieved. At the same time, they should prepare children to have the life-long capabilities and decision-making skills to face a society that is changing rapidly.

Being student-oriented in teaching: When using multimedia equipments, the whole teaching process is teacher-oriented. Teachers impart knowledge to students, ignoring students' presence and function in class. Teachers should conquer their laziness, teach more actively with enthusiasm, and be student-oriented with wholehearted commitment.

Choose proper equipment: combine modern method with traditional method Multimedia equipments are not omnipotent and by no means indicate modernization in teaching method. Not all aspects of teaching can be presented by these equipments. Teachers must choose proper teaching methods in accordance with teaching contents and objectives. Therefore, if traditional way of teaching is enough in conferring knowledge, teachers don't have to use multimedia equipments in class. Before each class, teachers must choose proper teaching method to enhance efficiency and results of teaching.

Better preparation before class: better PPT is a key aspect in a teaching process, which plays an important role in multimedia teaching method. A good PPT should concentrate on its contents and effects, not its form or flashiness. Teachers must pay attention to differences between PPT and teaching plan, making better PPT as teaching plan of high quality, which will be applied in class and benefit teaching quality.

Plan reasonably to improve teaching quality: Teachers can choose different multimedia equipments aiming at specific needs, plan and optimize teaching process properly. Teachers should avoid copying from textbook and sitting rigidly behind computer without interaction with students. They should communicate and interact with students actively, observe their reaction, adjust their teaching plan according to students' reaction, and inspire students to think. They can also provide more information to broaden students' mind and enhance teaching quality.

Education in accordance with individual differences: In class, teachers should notice students' individual differences to plan a lesson more carefully. A teaching plan must be perfected on the basis of class, major, students to cater the needs of specific class. Both

participation of students and teaching of teachers are essential to the whole teaching process. No matter what kind of teaching method teachers are using, they cannot neglect students and a class should be student-oriented.

Conclusion

Through the interaction with multimedia, the students are able to increase their problem solving capacity. The use of multimedia provides the students to gather information through media that encourages their imaginations, interests. The challenge to educators is to establish rigorous standards of quality in the products, services, and solutions offers to our youth. . Finally, Multimedia should be made compulsory and integrated in all secondary school curriculum, scheme of work, lesson note, lesson plan and in the classroom when teaching and learning take place because the concepts serves as learning and teaching aids which helps students to develop their problem solving ability to understand the concept better .

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